

Galaxy Evolution & the Mass-Size Relation in $z \sim 1$ Clusters

The Gemini CLuster Astrophysics Spectroscopic Survey (GCLASS)

Spectroscopic survey of **10** rich, IR-selected clusters at $0.86 < z < 1.34$ with Gemini/GMOS.

~500 cluster members altogether.

Now have **38 orbits** worth of HST WFC3 grism follow-up in F140W.

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F140W image of star-forming cluster galaxy

2D Grism spectrum

Grism redshifts have **~4 times higher accuracy** in identifying cluster members than photometric redshifts.

This **greatly increases** the cluster member sample with reliable size measurements from **274** \rightarrow **403**.

This **impressive accuracy level** can be used to identify a **large number** of cluster members in the grism sample that are **not** spectroscopically confirmed by GMOS.

Sizes are measured using a custom built GALFIT wrapper

Gives us a **robust measurement** of the cluster stellar mass-size relation at $z \sim 1$.

The **sérsic index** is an **effective morphological indicator** that is used to **track morphology** across the mass-size plane.

RESULTS

▶ **Larger sizes for star-forming galaxies** compared to the field environment, but **weaker size growth with stellar mass**.

▶ **Smaller sizes for quiescent galaxies** compared to the field, but **steeper size growth with stellar mass**.

▶ **Location of spectroscopically identified Post-starbursts (PSBs)** is **highly suggestive** of them being a **transition population** from star-forming \rightarrow quiescent.

▶ **Brightest Cluster Galaxies (BCGs)** approximately **follow the field quiescent mass-size relation** at $z \sim 1$.

▶ **Morphological breakdown confirms PSBs as transition population** in morphology as well as **stellar populations (spectra), stellar mass and size**.

CONCLUSION

There is a clear, strong link between a galaxy's stellar populations, stellar mass, size, morphology and quenching.